

Speculation on Energy Conservation and the Tsallis and Kaniadakis Distributions

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We have argued in previous notes that given the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, one may create different distributions based on a power law: { function in e_i/T } power function(parameter) such that for a special value of the parameter or for $e_i/T \ll 1$ one obtains the MB distribution. For $e_i/T \gg 1$, one expects: { e_i/T } function(parameter). For $e_i/T < 1$, the simplest polynomial expansions to consider are $1 - e_i/T$ and $1 - e_i/T + .5 e_i^2/T^2$. For e_i/T not small, one may wish to have the argument in e_i/T appear as being linear and so $-e_i/T + \sqrt{1 + k e_i/T}$ will achieve this result (in the Kaniadakis case). In particular, this holds because for $e_i/T \gg 1$, one wants to have e_i/T to a power in both cases. As a result, one may obtain the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions directly and check if they match experimental data. We suggest, however, that there is a second factor which must be considered.

The MB distribution is associated with two constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. The first is a standard constraint, but the second suggests a priori conservation of energy. In fact, conservation of energy is a key to the MB case. Now, even though $e_i > 0$ (both relativistically and nonrelativistically), mathematically a conservation law may be generalized to positive and negative values of e . In such a case, we argue that $p(e_i)p(-e_i) = 1$ because when accounting for energy $-e_i + e_i = 0$ for any e_i there is no special preference for the AND product probability. This consideration must be applied to the two power law distributions obtained above. The Tsallis (or $1 - e_i/T$ polynomial) approach does not yield $p(e_i)p(-e_i) = 1$, while the Kaniadakis approach does (as pointed out in (1)). Thus, we suggest that this implies that the Kaniadakis distribution should be linked with a priori energy conservation and the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$, while the Tsallis cannot. In other words, the Tsallis distribution should be linked with a different a priori constraint. We suggest that this is why one sees $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = F$ used as an a priori constraint in the Tsallis case. The lack of $p(e_i)p(-e_i) = 1$ for the Tsallis case prevents one from using $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$.

Power Law Distributions Linked to the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

As argued before, given the MB distribution: $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, one may consider an alternative power law type distribution based on:

(e_i/T) power function(parameter) for $e_i/T \gg 1$ ((1))

The question then becomes: What is the distribution for $e_i/T \ll 1$? Furthermore, one may ask: Is there a value of the parameter which makes the distribution equal the MB? If the answer is yes, then one may consider the following general forms:

{ function in e_i/T } power function2(parameter) ((2))

The simplest polynomial approximating the MB $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is (for $e_i/T \ll 1$) is

$$\{1 - f(q) e_i/T\} \text{ power } 1/f(q) \quad ((3))$$

This is in fact the Tsallis distribution for $f(q)=1-q$. For $e_i/T \gg 1$, one has: $\{-f(q)e_i/T\} \text{ power } 1/f(q)$ and so the above requirements are met.

A second polynomial form is to keep quadratic terms for $e_i/T \ll 1$:

$$\{1 - ke_i/T + .5 k k e_i e_i / T T\} \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is fine for the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, but not for the $e_i/T \gg 1$ as one requires $\{e_i/T\} \text{ power } f(k)$. ((5))

To achieve ((4)) and ((5)), one may consider the form:

$$\{\sqrt{1+kke_i e_i / T T} - ke_i/T\} \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((6))$$

For e_i/T , one may expand the sqrt, keeping the quadratic term, but for $e_i/T \gg 1$, the sqrt linearizes $e_i e_i / T T$ as needed. ((6)) is the Kaniadakis distribution.

As a result, one may readily create these two distributions and then hope that they describe data in nature, which seems to be the case in many scenarios.

The Question of Constraints

We now return to the MB distribution and note that it is directly linked with two constraints:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i)=1 \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{sum over } e_i \text{ } p(e_i)=E_{ave} \quad ((7b))$$

The first constraint is general, but the second is a statement of conservation of energy, we argue. Thus, in the MB case one deliberately considers energy being conserved in interactions. In principle, $e_i > 0$ relativistically and nonrelativistically, but mathematically conservation equations apply to both positive and negative e_i values. We suggest that this is an important idea as one must have:

$$p(e_i)p(-e_i) = 1 \quad ((8)) \quad \text{which is in fact the MB case, if one wishes to use } ((7b)), \text{ i.e.}$$

consider a priori energy conservation.

We next consider the Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases ((3)) and ((6)) above and note that:

$$p(e_i)p(-e_i) \neq 1 \quad \text{for the Tsallis case, but } p(e_i)p(-e_i)=1 \quad \text{for the Kaniadakis situation.}$$

We argue that this implies that $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ holds as an a priori constraint for the Kaniadakis case, but not for the Tsallis one. In other words, one should not consider the Tsallis case linked with ((7b)).

To see this idea in action, one may note that the Tsallis distribution also follows from the maximization of:

$\sum_i p(e_i)^q \{1 - p(e_i)^{1-q}\} / (1-q)$ subject to:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \text{ and } \sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i = F \quad ((8))$$

Thus, a different e_i constraint is used in the Tsallis case because the $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ one would imply that $p(e_i)p(-e_i) = 1$, which is not the result for the Tsallis scenario.

We note that (1) stresses that $p(e_i)p(-e_i) = 1$ for the Kaniadakis case, but argues that this is linked with special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may directly obtain the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions by arguing for a power law such that: $\{f(e_i/T)\} f(q)$, where q is a parameter and f , a function, should become: $\{e_i/T\}^q f(q)$ for $e_i/T \gg 1$, but should yield the MB $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for $e_i/T \ll 1$ and also for a certain value of the parameter. We argue that one may readily obtain two power distributions: $\{1 - (1-q)e_i/T\}^{1/(1-q)}$ (a linear polynomial approximation to $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the low e_i/T limit) and $\{\sqrt{1 + k e_i/T} - k e_i/T\}^{1/k}$ (a quadratic approximation to $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the low e_i/T limit). At this point, it is not really clear how these two distributions differ in principle. One may check if they match experimental data (which they do) and perhaps leave matters at that.

We suggest here, however, that there is a second consideration present. The MB distribution is linked with conservation of energy and the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. $e_i > 0$, but mathematically conservation of energy is a math statement that holds for both positive and negative e_i values. Thus, we argue that $p(e_i)p(-e_i) = 1$ must hold if the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ is used.

The Kaniadakis distribution automatically satisfies $p(e_i)p(-e_i) = 1$ and so we argue that it is associated with $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$, while the Tsallis, does not and so cannot be associated with this conservation of energy constraint. In practice, it is associated with the a priori constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i = F$.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. Physical Origin of the Power Law Tailed Statistical Distributions (2012) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1206.2250>